

D3.2 - First training module for Climate Smart Farming demonstration

Training on on-farm demonstrations

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List of Abbreviations

CFD	Climate Farm Demo
CFA	Climate Farm Advisor
NC	National Coordinator
PDF	Pilot Farm Demo
WP	Work Package

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Abstract

This document provides an outline for a training on the organisation of on-farm demonstrations on climate smart farming. It starts with a presentation on the basic principles for organising on-farm demonstrations, after which participants will participate in a real demo event and have a reflection exercise afterwards during which the demo event will be discussed based on the basic principles addressed in the presentation. The training will provide for a first time to national coordinators (NCs) and climate farm advisors (CFAs) during the general assemble meeting in Cork. They will be requested to replicate the training in their home countries. Depending on the NC's and CFA's further training needs regarding demo event organisation, an online training will be developed. Recordings of this training can be made available for a wider public and for new participants entering the project.

1.Introduction

This document provides an outline for a training on the organisation of on-farm demonstrations on climate smart farming. It will be centred around a case, which is a demo event. The training requires additional time before and after the demo event for participants to be introduced in the main principles of demo event organisation and to reflect afterwards on what they have witnessed during the participation in the demo event related to the highlighted principles.

2.Outline of the training

The training consists of three main parts:

1. **Introductory presentation** for the training participants with the key principles of on-farm demonstrations for Climate Smart Farming. This presentation can be translated to local languages and be used/adapted to national contexts. (1h)
2. **Participation in a demo event:** training participants participate in a real demo event, while focussing on specific principles introduced during the introductory presentation.
3. **Reflection on the demo event** with the training participants (1h).

2.1.Introductory presentation

A .ppt is developed for introducing the training participants into the main principles of the organisation of on-farm demonstrations ([Annex 1](#)). To allow training participants to get a good grip on the practicalities related to pre-event organisation, we suggest giving this presentation in duo with the demo event organiser of the demo event that will be visited afterwards. In the .ppt, questions to this demo event organiser are included. In this way a duo presentation will be done between the trainer providing the key principles and a practitioner explaining what it might mean in practice.

2.2.Participating in a demo event/case study

The training participants and trainer participate in a demo event as if they were real participants in the demo event, with the slight difference that they are asked to focus their observations on one specific aspect of demo event organisation.

A full explanation with preparation steps for the training organiser is added to [this document on Sharepoint](#). Each participant is asked to pick one observation card as presented in Figure 1 before or at the start of the event. These cards describe to which aspects of a demo event the participant must

pay specific attention during the demonstration. They could take some notes if they are afraid of forgetting some of the observations they make.

<p>1. Demo objective and set-up</p> <p>What is the main objective of this demo (Why, what, who)?</p> <p>What are positive and negative aspects of the programme, logistics, demo site, ...?</p> <p>How can the demo set up be improved?</p>		
<p>4. Demonstration of the climate issue</p> <p>How is the climate issue brought into the demo event, demonstrated or discussed?</p> <p>Is the demonstration explicitly linked to the climate change?</p> <p>Are the effects on climate adaptation and mitigation discussed during the demo?</p>		

Figure 1. Observation cards for training participants to take with them during the demo event.

2.3. Reflection

When the demo event ends, the training participants gather around a reflection canvas (Figure 2) in groups of 10 participants. The reflection starts by discussing the different aspects on the canvas. The facilitator first asks the person with the observation card on the specific aspect to share his/her observations and thoughts. Then the facilitator asks the others to react.

When the whole canvas is completed, the main findings are summarized into the conclusions (what were the highlights of the demo event, what could be improved, how could the project support them in improving future demo events). The outcomes of this final question should be passed to laure.triste@ilvo.vlaanderen.be, dmoniz@consulai.com, mmendonca@consulai.com, so they can take it into account for developing future trainings and capacity building materials.

Figure 2. Reflection canvas to discuss the observations made by the training participants during the training event.

3. Implementation of the training

A two-step training procedure will be put in place:

1. National Coordinators (NCs) and Climate Farm Advisors (CFAs) present during the GA meeting in Cork will be trained according to a slightly lighter version of the script outlined above. They will receive the full introductory presentation on the key principles for demo event organisation, but have a shorter reflection after the demo event than foreseen in this outline. Nevertheless, it will give the participants a good understanding about the principles of demo event organisation and how they can replicate the training in their own countries.
2. NCs (and the CFAs present during the GA meeting) are expected to replicate the training as as outlined above in their own countries for other CFAs and/or interested Pilot Demo Farmers. These replications can be organised during different occasions or events.

Depending on the expression of needs of the training participants in Cork, a complementary online training event will be developed in English and recorded to make it available for people entering the project in later stages.

In addition, videos will be developed on different aspects of demo event organisation for consultation by all project partners and a wider public, based on the materials developed in Deliverable 3.1 and 3.2.

Complementary to the video materials already developed during the NEFERTITI project¹, new videos will be generated with footage produced during the meeting in Cork on the following topics:

- Tutorial on the 6 steps of organising a demo event on climate smart farming
- The practical implications of preparing for a demo event
- The use of props in demo events
- The importance of reflection in a demo event

Although ClimateFarmDemo focusses on the organisation of on-farm demonstration event, we don't entirely exclude virtual demo events in the project. In the coming years, online training events on the organisation of virtual demo events will be organised for those who are interested to also build capacity in the consortium on this type of demo event organisation.

¹ Six steps to design a demo event:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VhnM6C8Nv_M&list=PLOYrtkIDkcdSeJ8vOzigymg-0LZUZxBWF&index=8

How to increase interaction during a demo event:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZZ2MPjiGh_Q&list=PLOYrtkIDkcdSeJ8vOzigymg-0LZUZxBWF&index=1

How to prepare a demo-event:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dIAIBeMTVbk&list=PLOYrtkIDkcdSeJ8vOzigymg-0LZUZxBWF&index=12>

Annex 1: presentation on key principles for demo event organisation

 CLIMATE
FARM
DEMO

Organising demo events on
climate smart farming

Cork- 10/10/2023

Laure Triste (ILVO)

***Can the real farm
demonstrator please stand up?***

What is a demonstration event?

- "The action or process of showing the existence or truth of something by giving proof or evidence" (Oxford Dictionary)
- "A practical exhibition and explanation of how something works or is performed" (Oxford Dictionary)
- "An authentic learning space where farmers and other stakeholders can explore and discuss agricultural practices together in a socially and physically embedded manner." (Cooreman, 2021)

Why demonstration events?

- Play a key role in extending climate farm solutions to more farmers
- Provide practical, tangible experiences of farming methods and technologies that participants can subsequently use to improve their own farming practices.
- Allow climate solutions/ AMM's be demonstrated in situ;
- Provide an opportunity for the farmer to share their experiences;
- Leverage the advisory and support efforts with the demo farmer by reaching more farmers;
- Build trust between CFA, AKIS actors and farmers;
- Highlight the initial starting point (first event) and progress made on the farm over time (at second and subsequent events)

Rules for a Climate Farm Demo Event

- Ideally organised on a Pilot Demonstration Farm (PDF), Lighthouse Farm or Experimental Farm;
- A minimum attendance of around 10 farmers;
- An event objective relating to the demonstration of climate smart farming approaches or technologies;
- Facilitates farmer-to-farmer learning and exchange of ideas;
- Pre-registered on the project website;
- Post-evaluated on the project website.

Organising On-Farm Demonstrations

<https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/demo-design-guide/>

Design Guide for CFD On-Farm Demos

- | | | |
|-----------------|---|---|
| | | 1. PLANNING THE DEMO EVENT |
| Prepare | | 2. MAKING THE BEST USE OF THE HOST FARMER |
| | | 3. FARM DEMO SET-UP |
| | | 4. PROMOTION OF EVENTS |
| Deliver | | 5. LEARNING AND FACILITATION METHODS |
| Evaluate | | 6. MONITORING, EVALUATION AND FOLLOW-UP |

1 – Planning a demo event

Set clear objectives and key messages

“Why are we organising this demo event?”

“What do we want to demonstrate?”

“Who is the target audience?”

“How should we set-up and facilitate the demo event ?”

1 – Planning a demo event : **WHY?**

Stage in behaviour change process of target audience	Demo objective
Farmers are not yet acknowledging a problem	Building awareness on the effects of climate change and climate policy, identify opportunities, communicate the importance of change
Farmers acknowledge the problem, but are not yet ready to change	Make clear what's in it for them. Try to acknowledge their personal motivators and act upon it.
Farmers are getting ready to change	Demonstrate and promote climate solutions and research innovations. Train farmers and develop skills on specific AMM
Farmers are testing new change	Train farmers and develop skills on specific AMM Train farmers on the implementation of climate policy Share experiences Co-create knowledge with the participants on specific climate issues or solutions
Farmers are trying to maintain and grow the new behaviour	Network farmers and other actors, to strengthen cooperation and partnerships. Debrief lessons learned.

1 – Planning a demo event : **WHAT?**

Make GHG emissions (reductions) and climate (adaptation) effects real

Use farmer's environmental and economic performance figures and data from the audits

Limit the number of topics

Use the National Knowledge exchange plan and DAP to support the bottom-up selection of topics

1 – Planning a demo event : **WHAT?**

Demo event 1

*Present baseline and figures
 Share AMP*

Demo event 2

*Review progress made
 Demonstrate good practices and new AMM implemented*

Demo event 3

*Review progress made
 Present figures of the audit
 Link audit results to AMM taken
 Refer to benefits related to rewarding mechanisms*

1 – Planning a demo event : **WHO?**

Open to wide audience (preferred for majority of the demos)

Restricted to other PDFs in the region

Targeting all sectors

Targeting a specific sector

Wide geographical area

Specific geographical area

Early adopters (change mindset)

Laggards (more conservative mindset)

Farmer audience

Wider AKIS

1 – Planning a demo event : **HOW?**

The organisation team

Climate Farm Advisor	Logistic coordinator
Actors from the agri-food chain, re-searchers, media, ...	Facilitator

Host PDF

Share responsibilities!

In-person vs. Virtual

Choose a suitable date

Season

Time during the day

Other events

Testimony of demo organiser

How did you define the why, what, who and how of your demo event?

2 – MAKING THE BEST USE OF THE HOST FARMER

Make the host PDF central to the demo event

- Perform interview led by a facilitator
- Give participants the opportunity to ask questions to the host
- Give participants the opportunity to give feedback and own experiences with the host

2 – MAKING THE BEST USE OF THE HOST FARMER

Public speaker

- Introvert
- Extravert

Relatability

- Similar 'real life' conditions as average
- Pioneer farmer

Suitability

- Demo objective/topic
- Geographical accessibility
- Physical accessibility
- Facilities
- Comfort and safety

Good farmer

- Example for peers
- Respected
- Opinion leader
- Central in local networks
- Embracing change

Testimony of demo organiser

How did you engage the host farmer in the organisation of the demo event taking into account the characteristics mentioned?

3 – Farm Demo set-up

Demo event programme

Welcome/introduction

Practical demonstration

Facilitated discussion or Q&A

Participant reflection on key messages

Closure: Clear conclusion/take home messages

Evaluation of the event

Time for social interaction

3 – Farm Demo set-up

Farm Walks

- Include description of the stands/stops
- Include time for Q&A at each stop
- Identify opportunities for participant engagement (e.g; test, assess something, ...)
- Pre-plan the route and allocate time

3 – Farm Demo set-up

Boards

- Few text
- Visuals
- Take home messages

Props

- Animals, Materials,
- Tools, Score cards,
- Games , ...

Handouts

- Short
- To the point

3 – Farm Demo set-up

PDF information sheet

Template developed in D3.1
Key characteristics of the PDF and audit

Testimony of demo organiser

*How did you decide on the props to be
used during the demo event?*

4 – Promotion and registration

Make a clear invitation

Choose appropriate communication channels

Register on the platform

4 – Promotion and registration

Convincing farmers to join a climate demo event

Stress the impact of climate change on their daily lives

Highlight potential cost savings and enhanced profits

Outplay their social responsibility

Stress the current and future policy obligations

Testimony of demo organiser

*Which promotion actions did you take
prior to the event?*

5 - Learning and facilitation methods

A good facilitator is key!

- Body language: gestures, facial expression
- Respect host farmer and participants
- Communicate clearly
- Listen and promote talk to action
- Facilitate discussion

5 - Learning and facilitation methods

Group size and composition

Impacts the format of the demo event

Homogenous groups vs. Diverse groups

Familiarity amongst participants

5 - Learning and facilitation methods

Learning methods

Relate learning content to farming practice

- Relate to the broader context
- Make use of the host PDF

Engage participants in active knowledge exchange

- Offer opportunities for p2p knowledge exchange
- Offer experiences and surprise participants
- Create a stimulating setting

Use a variety in learning activities

5 - Learning and facilitation methods

Stimulate reflection: ORID

Testimony of demo organiser

*Which facilitation and learning methods
did you include in the demo event?*

6 - Evaluation and follow-up

Monitoring and evaluation

1. Monitor

- Point a responsible as monitor
- Choose tools to observe what happens at your demo event
- Collect and report on what happened and what participants learned

2. Evaluate

- Analyse the collected data
- Return back to the set objectives

3. Draw lessons to improve next demo events

- Organise a moment for team reflection

6 - Evaluation and follow-up

CFD Monitoring & Evaluation tools

Exit poll

Evaluation tool

Complete post-event form on the platform

6 - Evaluation and follow-up

Follow up

For participants

- Email with thanking, key messages and take-home materials
- Share participant list (with consent)
- Share potential follow up actions and other ongoing activities
- Provide support

For non-participants

- Provide a report or video
- Use different source of media
- Release press articles/invite journalists
- Make trial publicly accessible

Testimony of demo organiser

How will you evaluate and follow-up on the demo event?

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